

Guidance and Counselling Services for Employability through Libraries in Higher Educational Institutions in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Today's labour market has become increasingly complex, and the average career or job seeker has been left stranded. New information is required at every turn to empower the career or job seeker to know about the proper education and training for getting a job; to know about the job market, to find suitable employers; to know about vacancy positions, to gain knowledge about preparing application and resumes, to prepare for interviews; to be able to choose right career, as well as acquire skills and capabilities to acquire and manage the chosen career. Libraries, as an integral part of the educational system, can contribute much towards empowering students with necessary skills required for the future workforce, especially in Higher Educational Institutions (HEI).

Method: The paper adopted a documentary research method where recent studies and other related literature are gathered, reviewed and analysed with a view to underscore the roles of libraries in delivering guidance and counselling services to students with particular reference to HEI in Nigeria.

Results/Findings: Several strategies for providing career information services in libraries to assist students in making career decisions were identified in the paper: providing staff and students access to relevant publications on all aspects of career planning; holding career talks to highlight the library's resources and services specifically related to career information; creating awareness among students about how to search, assess, and choose career information from the vast ocean of information. Inadequate career

information materials, students' lack of interest in their career development and librarian's inertia were among the issues that libraries encounter when delivering career information services.

Conclusion: The paper concludes that libraries in higher education institution can supports students through the provision of various resources and strategies of career information service delivery to cope up with their educational and career needs.

Recommendations: Libraries should live up to their expectation, they should be well equipped with resources including career related information for helping the students to relive their problems and realize their dreams through guidance and counselling.

Keywords: Academic libraries, career information services, guidance and counselling, higher educational institutions, Nigeria.

Introduction

Student career preparedness is one of the important goals of higher education globally (Brosnan, 2020). That is why students, their families and lecturers tie employment and career advancement benefits to investment in higher education (Brosnan, 2020). Eagan, et al. (2016), conducted a study on expectation after graduation where majority of the respondents agreed that "preparing students for employment after college" was "essential". As a result, HEI encounter growing students and parents' expectations of return on educational investments in competitive job markets, where the relative value of university degrees is decreasing (Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2017). Thus, HEI are expected to demonstrate their value and support for student success in career placement and advancement more than ever before (Pun & Kubo, 2017).

To response to the students and parents' expectations, HEI must explore ways to improve student employability, especially with the labour market becoming complex more and more due to the exerting impact of modern technologies, creating serious concern for the average career or job seeker. Searching for job has become a struggle among graduates and those already employed who want to change jobs and careers. This will require job seekers to have access to timely and accurate information to conduct an effective job search. They need information at various stages of their career search. As future job seekers, students need information about various professions that are available to them and the perceived marketability of each of the professions, qualifications required, the

responsibilities to be undertaken, as well as the general nature of the job (Koovakkai & Jalaja, 2006; Esnas & Sammy, 2011; Mporananayo & Andala, 2018). Based on this, Bennett, et al. (2015) suggested that to develop a whole-institution approach which will enhance student employability, it will make sense to use expertise across discipline-specific and cross-discipline training providers in the HEI.

In this paper, we present the role of library in enhancing student employability through guidance and counselling services. Specifically, the paper is designed to highlight the strategies through which libraries can deliver career information services an aspect of guidance and counselling services to empower students with skills necessary to enhance their career or job searching as students as well as graduate. Secondly, to identify problems associated with the qualitative career information services delivery in HEI in Nigeria and make recommendations.

Review of Related Literature

The Concept of Career Guidance and Counselling Services

Guidance and counselling services are the assistance given to students to make far reaching decisions under considerable uncertainty regarding the continuation of education and the transition into the labour market (McNally, 2016; Heckman et al., 2018). Specifically, career guidance is the assistance given to students to make informed decisions through the provision of career related information, counselling, mentoring, or first-hand work experience. While counselling services generally focuses on providing information and advice, work experience placements which allow students to learn about work organization in general as well as specific occupations and employers offering apprenticeships (Fitzenberger, et al., 2020). The authors further stated that for a seamless transition from school to labour market or work place and for informed decision making, career guidance is needed. In the context of this paper, guidance and counselling represent a number of user services offered by the librarian to library users, they include but not limited to literature search, reference service, user education, user advice, career talk and bibliotherapy. These services are aimed at improving student's confidence level, personality traits and employability (Sakkaravarthi & Thanuskodi, 2020). Different career guidance and counselling needs have been identified and reported in the literature as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Career guidance and counselling needs

Career guidance and counselling needs	Sources
Awareness and development of personal abilities needs; professional and career-related skills need Career planning needs	Cojocariu & Puiu, 2014; Crisan et al., 2015 Chircu 2014; Crisan et al., 2015
Decision making needs	Crisan et al., 2015; Sun & Yuen, 2012
Career information needs	Cojocariu & Puiu, 2014; Crisan et al., 2015
Academic information needs Job hunting, job search skills need	Chircu, 2014 Chircu, 2014; Litoiu & Oproiu, 2012
Labor market information needs Career-related services like curriculum vitae (CV) writing, interview skills need	Chircu, 2014 Litoiu & Oproiu, 2012
Stress management needs, occupational guidance, and information about placements and internships needs	Sultana, 2004; Szilagyi, 2008

The benefits of guidance and counselling services were also documented in the literature (Abubakar, 2016; Akpochafo, 2020). Fundamentally school system integrates guidance and counseling services to address the overwhelming ignorance among young people about career choices and personality maladjustment (Mghweno & Baguma, 2013). Adequate provision of these services will enable students in the schools to understand themselves, their abilities, their potentials and develop enhanced capacity for making wise choices and perform well in their studies (Awoyemi & Odeniyi, 2014). Rawatlal and Pillay (2017) have rightly acknowledged that career education provided to students will further promotes career information health of the students, and this will reduces career insecurity and anxiety associated with career indecision.

Roles of Libraries in Guidance and Counselling

The role of libraries in guidance and counselling services cannot be overstated. Libraries has a long standing tradition of providing information and services for every individual in the society, be it for education, research, leisure, employment etc. The library has everything for everyone. Underscoring the role of libraries in career guidance, Anderson (1992) stated that libraries can play a significant role in providing the information required

to be informed, and up-to-date as well as for a career or job search. The author emphasizes the necessity for career job information and the role of libraries as clear-cut service providers to enhance the delivery of this information.

Libraries are known for providing right information to the right people at the right time and at all times (Balasubramanian, et al., 2013). In their contribution, Swamy, et al. (2014) stated that libraries are invaluable resources, and convenient places for locating information on job openings, potential contacts, colleges, financial aid, vocational training, businesses, careers, and resume writing. The authors further stated that libraries frequently have subscriptions to various trade magazines that can provide information on occupations and industries; training and employment opportunities. Furthermore, Swamy et al., (2014) stressed that libraries can play a much important role in imparting career guidance at different setting. For example, in formal education, library is described as 'heart of education'; and libraries in higher education are committed to provide independent learning environment to students, in addition to educating the students on how to effectively access and utilize information and information resources print or electronic within the library or even outside the library to support their academic and future career. Consequently, it can be inferred that the success of career guidance in educational institutions depends upon the efficient library system (Swamy et al., 2014).

Describing the role of librarians, Wiley and Williams (2015) stated that it is worthy to note that the role of librarians now includes career advisory services to students who are undecided on a career path. The authors further argued that when librarians embrace their roles as academic advisors, students are enlightened and become sure about their future career paths. Farsana and Mini (2020) describe libraries as the rational service providers, and librarians as the rational resource persons to enhance the delivery of required career information. They further inferred that librarians are in a better position of being aware of career resources than any other career professional.

Library stands as a viable tool for making career decisions (Obikwelu et al., 2022) and librarians, with their abilities in knowledge organization and dissemination skills, can significantly support young people in their pursuit of their dreams, guiding them in their studies and preparing them for future careers. Thus, it has been described as a treasure house of knowledge, an organized collection of books and other materials (printed and non-printed) for study, research and recreation (Achebe, 2016). These collection of information resources provide individuals with information for professional growth and personal development including healthy career decisions (Obikwelu et al., 2022). The

authors summed it all where they stated that library as a repository of knowledge, can enable access to different career information while the librarian serves as guidance.

Discussing further, empirical studies reported on the roles of libraries and librarians in delivering career information, guidance and counselling services to students, unemployed graduates and other youth for example in their research entitled “job information needs and seeking behaviour of graduates in Bayelsa State”, Efe and Nnenda (2022) found that Nigerian graduates have a number of job information needs including information about job vacancies; resume preparation and how to prepare for job interviews. The graduates consult variety of sources for their job information such as relatives/friends, internet sources, newspapers, and the radio. However, they seldom consult the library. The greatest challenge facing the graduates was finding accurate and reliable job information. This implied that libraries have a big role to play in the battle to create jobs awareness and better the lot of the citizenry of Nigeria (Irenea, 2020).

Obikwelu et al., (2022) while reviewing literature for their study established that students make wrong career preferences due to poor information among other factors; consequently, the authors recommended and highlighted a significant need to reposition the roles of the librarians and the services of the libraries to include career guidance services. Because there are fewer graduate jobs available and more graduates graduating from our higher education institutions, finding a job in Nigeria has become a fight and a contest of the strongest (Efe & Nnenda, 2022). The authors further stated that the high rate of unemployment seems to be one of the characteristics that define developing countries, despite the fact that unemployment is a global phenomenon. This means that the government alone will not and cannot succeed alone without the input of other sectors of society, such as libraries whose roles include empowering the unemployed with necessary information to plan their career and ultimately secure a job.

Similarly, Otwine et al., (2023) stress the importance of raising students' awareness of occupational information in the schools about the rapidly evolving nature of work and how technology may help students transition into their careers and lessen the problem of youth unemployment that exists worldwide. However, in a situation where there is no mechanism put in place to provide career information services to help students meet their career needs, studies indicated that students may often suffer negative career thoughts (Ogbuanya et al., 2018), career indecision (Mansor & Rashid, 2013), and a low level of career readiness (Mahmud et al., 2019).

Strategies for Disseminating Career Information in Libraries

The role of libraries as information disseminating agency is at an enviable position to successfully serve its user community in their career information need. The following are some of the strategies libraries can use in disseminating career information services in higher educational institutions:

Developing career information resources

As part of the library's collection development policy, the library will select, acquire, organise and disseminate relevant publications on all aspects of career planning to staff and students in the institution. There are a variety of publications on career planning ranging from books, magazines, newspapers, journals, periodicals, business directories, bulletins, etc both in print and electronic format that the library can acquire. Other important resources include competitive/aptitude examinations being conducted by governmental and non-governmental agencies which will help the student seeking for job to prepare for aptitude test or examinations both written and personal interview.

Online access to resources

To ensure access to online resources, libraries can set up a Career Information Resource Portal, which will provide access to essential career information such as job announcements, CV preparation, and interviews; in addition, the library may also provide access to several databases that job seekers will find particularly useful for their business content such as Business Periodicals Index.

Organizing career talks

The library can organise career talks in form of lectures, seminars, workshops, panel discussions periodically with aim of showcasing the resources and services of the library specifically relating to career information; and also providing information about various vocations or professions useful for career seeking students. Job search instruction can similarly be assimilated into the job search seminars (DeHart, 1996). Career talks can increase the career readiness of the students especially in the aspect of career planning in order to fulfil the demands of the career market (Greene & Staff, 2012). In organizing career talks, the librarian may invite professional career counsellors as well as other professionals from different profession to talk to students. This will prepare students well for the job search and give them a competitive edge in identifying and obtaining a

satisfying job (DeHart, 1996). Students, especially the first-year students should have an opportunity to attend these classes/seminars to make decision about the courses to be taken and also in the selection of their future careers.

Film shows

To organizing career talk, the library may also organize film shows - however, this is one of the important activities of the school library, but academic libraries may use the same approach to disseminate career information through film strips. The librarian must ensure that the film strips are made on the various aspects of a particular item, including screening them on various career options, professions, or occupations. There must be commentary along with the film strips to make it more useful.

Displays and exhibitions

Displays and exhibitions of relevant information sources related to career opportunities. Some of the items to be display may include charts, posters, leaflets, and newspaper cuttings on bulletin boards and walls. The display of these materials may take place within and outside the library. A good example is that of Georgia College Library that displayed the Career Bookshelf containing miscellaneous materials such as Career Center pamphlets, staff business cards and ever-changing promotional posters as a one-stop area for job searching and career preparation (Davis & Pope, 2012).

Job announcement

The library may scan and display job announcements in newspapers, Internet and notice board. According to Davis and Pope (2012) through this the library will make promotional efforts, which included press releases, signage on campus, social media posts, website content, campus emails and an article in the local newspaper all targeting job hunters in the institution.

Career information literacy skills

Libraries can provide instruction on career information literacy skills as well as information and digital literacy (IDL) to create awareness among the students regarding how to search, evaluate, and select career information from the vast ocean of information within and outside the campus environment. The IDL will position students well for graduate level employment and will equip them with life skills which are transferable to the demands

of an increasingly complex digital world (University of Sheffield, 2017). Students should be taught how to search the Internet and important sites they should look in for career information. They should equally be train in soft skills such as oral and written communication skills, resume writing, cover letter writing, web searching, sending e-mails, sending attachment files, posting of resumes in the net, etc.

Career awareness service

This is a sort of reference service usually offered on individual bases to students regarding a particular job on request. As part of their professional responsibilities reference librarian may allocate one hour per day to assist patrons with their career planning needs. Some of the effective methods for career awareness services are - notification lists, career awareness bulletin, newspaper clipping services, selective dissemination of information, etc. Clack (1979).

Collaboration between academic libraries and career centres

This arrangement is one of the most successful strategies to provide students with effective career guide. Pun (2019) stated that preparing students for career opportunities can be highly rewarding for academic librarians, and one way to expand on this work is through collaboration with campus partners. Literature study revealed successful partnership between academic libraries with careers service units, and collaboration with teaching faculty in developing instruction and workshops, online library guides, assessment, and consultation services for career assignments on career paths and occupations research (Howard 2017; Lafferty, 2019).

Problems of Career Guidance in Academic Libraries - Nigerian Perspective

Despite the potential of libraries in supporting students' career needs, many academic libraries in HEI in Nigeria have not yet integrated career services into their current list of services. The need for such services is quite important because, students in the 21st Century are overwhelmed with different kinds of information (verified and unverified) and libraries play a crucial role in providing substantial information for the growth and development of students (Saibakumo, 2021). Recently, Victor-Aigbodion (2021) discovered that university libraries in Nigeria rarely provide career information resources and services to their students. The university library's inability to provide such importance services suggests a need for a thorough review of its services and operations to enhance efficiency and effectiveness.

The problems associated with career services in the libraries include but not limited to inadequate career information materials. Some libraries do have the career information materials, but they may be scattered frequently in more than one place within the library. Too often, however, students may not know where those materials are located, and even if they stumble upon the materials, they may not know how to effectively use the materials (Lorenzen & Batt, 2019) due to lack of information skills.

There is also lack of collaboration between academic libraries and other stakeholders such as guidance and counsellors and or the Career Planning Department of the institution as well as lecturers in general. On the part of students, many are not showing much interest in their career development as such they do not seek for career information (Moly, 2010). Moly also identified librarian's inertia as yet another challenge affecting career information delivery in libraries in developing countries including Nigeria. Many a times librarians are satisfied with the traditional services and they do not want to stretch out themselves in serving the user community in new areas.

Conclusion

Among the goals of HEI is to produce graduates who are employable. Thus, graduate students are expected to have acquired necessary skills for various jobs in the market or for self-employment. This means that student career preparedness is an important goal of higher education and that is why Mawson and Haworth (2018) postulated that student employability and skills are a key priority for the Higher Education Institution globally. The nation's development lies on the shoulders of the young graduates hence, there is a need to equip them with necessary information, guidance, counselling so as to enable them to take lead role in the nation's development.

This paper has demonstrated how libraries in higher education institution can supports students through the provision of resources and services to cope up with their educational and career needs. Various strategies of career information service delivery libraries can use in helping students to meet their challenges of today and tomorrow were discussed. The paper was concluded by a discourse on the problems associated with library's efforts in providing career information services to students. However, the paper noted despites these challenges, libraries in developed nations were doing well while libraries in Nigeria are lagging behind.

Recommendations

1. Career information sources should be made available and accessible to students. The library should play an active role in the dissemination of career information to students. This is to help in the diffusion of the information to enhance career decision making.
2. The library should ensure that information on various self-employment opportunities is made available for the students and guide them to choose suitable trade as their future occupation. The librarian should provide the students with details like prerequisites for starting an enterprise, sources of finance, raw material, process of product, and marketing the finish product. This will enable students prepare for employment rather than depending to be employed.
3. The libraries should also provide information to students on various higher educational opportunities available within and outside the country. This will guide those students who would like to continue their education further.
4. For the libraries that have some resources on career development but are scattered frequently in more than one place. There is the need to bring them together in one place and educate students about their availability and how to access them.
5. There is the need for reference librarians in the academic libraries to provide career awareness services as part of the reference services of the library, and ensure that all related material on career guidance should be made available, including the announcements of jobs and related news items to the aspiring students. The reference librarian may take the advantage of the Short Messaging Service (SMS) and emails to push job-related information to registered students. Such innovative services are expected to enhance the library's visibility and relevance among students.
6. The libraries should have a close collaboration with other stakeholders such as guiding and counselling unit and Directorate of Employment with a view to organize career talk, career fair, seminar on job searching etc. especially for first year undergraduate students.

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